

Predictive Value of TyG Index for Contrast-Induced Nephropathy in Non-Diabetic Patients with NSTEMI Undergoing Percutaneous Coronary Intervention

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Abstract

Objective: The frequency of contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN) in non-diabetic patients with NSTEMI undergoing PCI, stratified according to high and low TyG index groups.

Material and Methods: This analytical cross-sectional study was conducted at the Rawalpindi Institute of Cardiology between September 2025 and February 2026. A total of 250 non-diabetic patients with confirmed NSTEMI undergoing PCI were enrolled through consecutive sampling. Patients were stratified into high-TyG (>8.65) and low-TyG (<8.65) groups. Continuous variables were compared using the independent-samples t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, and categorical variables were compared using the chi-square test. Multivariable logistic regression was used to assess the independent association between TyG and CIN, and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis was used to evaluate discriminatory performance.

Results: The overall mean age was 58.40 ± 10.19 years, and 175 patients (70.0%) were male. CIN developed in 37 patients (14.8%). CIN occurred more frequently in the high-TyG group than in the low-TyG group (20.0% vs 9.6%, $p = 0.033$), with an unadjusted odds ratio of 2.35 (95% CI: 1.12-4.93). In the primary adjusted model, high TyG remained independently associated with CIN (adjusted OR: 4.04, 95% CI: 1.64-9.92; $p = 0.002$). Older age, higher baseline creatinine, and greater contrast volume were also independent predictors. In sensitivity analysis, the continuous TyG index remained significantly associated with CIN (adjusted OR: 7.58 per 1-unit increase, 95% CI: 2.32-24.73; $p < 0.001$), and the association persisted when eGFR replaced baseline creatinine in the model.

Conclusion: A higher TyG index is independently associated with an increased risk of CIN in non-diabetic patients with NSTEMI undergoing PCI with roughly double the unadjusted risk of CIN and remained an independent predictor after adjustment, while older age, poorer baseline renal function, and greater contrast exposure also contributed importantly to CIN risk.

Keywords: Triglyceride-Glucose Index; Contrast-Induced Nephropathy; Non-ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction; Percutaneous Coronary Intervention; Acute Kidney Injury, Pakistan

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Introduction

Contrast-induced nephropathy (CIN), broadly characterized by an acute reduction in kidney function after intravascular iodinated contrast administration.

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Remains a clinically consequential complication of percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI).¹⁻² Although contemporary practice emphasizes preventive approaches most notably structured hydration protocols and strict limitation of contrast volume CIN continues to be linked to substantial adverse consequences, including greater morbidity, prolonged hospitalization, increased healthcare expenditures, and poorer long-term renal and cardiovascular outcomes.³⁻⁴

Insulin resistance (IR) has emerged as an important contributor to vascular injury and renal vulnerability, with pathophysiologic effects that extend beyond overt diabetes.⁵ In this context, the triglyceride-glucose (TyG) index, derived from fasting triglyceride and glucose levels, has gained

prominence as a convenient and reproducible surrogate marker of IR.⁶ Consistent with this framework, elevated TyG index values have been associated with renal impairment and adverse cardiovascular events across diverse patient populations, suggesting potential utility for risk stratification in clinical practice.⁷⁻⁹ Recent investigations have begun to clarify the relationship between the TyG index and CIN among patients undergoing PCI. Aktas et al. reported that, in non-diabetic patients with non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI), those in the highest TyG quartile experienced a markedly higher risk of CIN (odds ratio [OR] 6.58, 95% confidence interval [CI] 2.12-20.40; TyG cut-off 9.17; area under the curve [AUC] 0.712) (10). Similarly, Gursoy and Baydar found in a cohort of 350 non-diabetic NSTEMI patients undergoing PCI that a TyG index > 8.65 was independently associated with CIN (OR 2.5, 95% CI 1.3-4.6), with an AUC of 0.66611 for CIN prediction. Despite these encouraging findings, an important gap remains.⁹

Much of the available evidence has been generated in broader PCI cohorts, and comparatively limited data address the predictive performance of the TyG index specifically in non-diabetic NSTEMI patients undergoing PCI a clinically high-risk subgroup given their acute inflammatory milieu and frequent exposure to contrast media.¹¹ Further validation is therefore needed to determine whether the TyG index provides independent prognostic information in this setting and whether it adds value beyond established clinical predictors and conventional risk assessment tools. Accordingly, the aim of the present study is to evaluate whether the TyG index independently predicts CIN in non-diabetic patients with NSTEMI undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention.

Material and Methods

This single-center, analytical, and cross-sectional study enrolled consecutive non-diabetic patients presenting with NSTEMI to the catheterization laboratory of Rawalpindi Institute of Cardiology, Pakistan. The study period corresponded to the 6-month recruitment window defined in the approved protocol.

Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18 to 80 years with confirmed NSTEMI who were non-diabetic, as determined by history or an HbA1c level below 6.5%, undergoing PCI with drug-eluting stent(s), had a baseline estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) greater than 60 ml/min/1.73 m², and were willing to provide informed consent. Exclusion criteria included prior diabetes mellitus, pre-existing end-stage renal disease or maintenance dialysis, contrast exposure within 7 days before PCI, procedures requiring more than 200 ml of contrast volume, cardiogenic shock or hemodynamic instability, and known autoimmune or inflammatory disorders affecting metabolism.

The sample size for this study was determined using the

WHO sample size calculator, based on assumptions derived from the reference study (9). With a two-sided test, a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), and a study power of 80% ($1 - \beta = 0.80$), the required sample size was estimated to be 125 patients in each group. Accordingly, the total sample size for the study was 250 patients.

After approval from the Institutional Review Board and CPSP, 250 patients were enrolled. Clinical information, including age (years), sex, duration of symptoms (minutes), smoking history, hypertension (mm Hg), body mass index (kg/m²), and family history of coronary artery disease (CAD), was recorded. During the pre-PCI phase, fasting blood samples were collected from eligible patients to assess triglyceride and glucose levels (using enzymatic colorimetric assay) for TyG index calculation; HbA1c to confirm non-diabetic status; and serum creatinine (using enzymatic method) and eGFR, as per hospital protocol. The projected Mehran risk score for CIN was also documented.

During the PCI procedure, the type and total volume of contrast medium administered (measured in mL/kg) were recorded. Additional procedural details, including vascular access site, number and type of stents used, and any intra-procedural complications, were also noted. In the post-PCI phase, patients were monitored with repeat serum creatinine testing at 48 and 72 hours to assess changes in renal function. Urine output and clinical signs suggestive of acute kidney injury (AKI) were also monitored. CIN was diagnosed based on a rise in serum creatinine of > 0.3 mg/dL or > 50% from baseline within the 48–72-hour post-procedure period.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the study findings, quality control measures were maintained throughout the study. Data were collected by trained personnel using a standardized proforma to ensure uniform documentation and reduce observer variation. Patients were enrolled strictly according to predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to minimize selection bias. All laboratory investigations were performed in the hospital laboratory using standardized protocols and calibrated equipment. Fasting blood samples were obtained before PCI in all patients to ensure consistency in TyG index measurement, while serum creatinine was assessed at baseline, 48 hours, and 72 hours after PCI according to a uniform protocol. CIN was diagnosed using a predefined operational definition. Procedural details were recorded systematically at the time of PCI to minimize recording bias. In addition, all data were reviewed regularly for completeness and accuracy, and any discrepancies were verified from the original records before final entry.

The study was approved by the Research & Ethical Review Committee of Rawalpindi Institute of Cardiology via approval number No: RIC/RERC/18/25. Written informed consent was obtained from participants.

Data were entered into a secure database and analyzed with IBM SPSS version 26 was. Quantitative variables, including

TyG index, age, BMI, fasting triglycerides, fasting glucose, serum creatinine, eGFR, and contrast volume, were expressed as mean \pm SD or median with interquartile range, as appropriate, while categorical variables, including CIN development, gender, hypertension, smoking status, and radial/femoral access site, were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Results

A total of 250 non-diabetic patients with NSTEMI undergoing PCI were included in the analysis, with 125 patients in each TyG category. Overall, the mean age was 58.40 ± 10.19 years, 175 patients (70.0%) were male, and CIN developed in 37 patients (14.8%). The mean TyG index for the overall cohort was 8.72 ± 0.39 , baseline serum creatinine was 0.83 ± 0.10 mg/dL, baseline eGFR was 95.14 ± 14.86 mL/min/1.73 m², and the mean contrast volume used during PCI was 126.49 ± 18.33 mL (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of non-diabetic NSTEMI patients undergoing PCI stratified by TyG group

Variable	Low TyG (<8.65) (n=125)	High TyG (>8.65) (n=125)	p-value
Age, years	59.82 \pm 9.33	56.97 \pm 10.83	0.026
Male sex, n (%)	88 (70.4)	87 (69.6)	1.000
Hypertension, n (%)	51 (40.8)	63 (50.4)	0.162
Smoking, n (%)	58 (46.4)	50 (40.0)	0.371
Killip class I/II/III, n (%)	93/28/4	99/23/3	0.663
BMI, kg/m ²	25.73 \pm 2.14	29.41 \pm 2.15	<0.001
Time since symptom onset, hours	6.00 [3.80-8.30]	5.90 [3.70-8.52]	0.918
Troponin I/T, ng/mL	1.06 [0.70-1.70]	1.02 [0.70-1.60]	0.560
Fasting blood glucose, mg/dL	90.14 \pm 9.27	101.57 \pm 8.37	<0.001

TyG index	8.38 \pm 0.15	9.05 \pm 0.21	<0.001
aseline creatinine, mg/dL	0.84 \pm 0.10	0.82 \pm 0.10	0.196
eGFR, mL/min/1.73 m²	93.66 \pm 14.30	96.63 \pm 15.31	0.114
Contrast volume, mL	125.94 \pm 19.58	127.03 \pm 17.04	0.640
Radial access, n (%)	104 (83.2)	93 (74.4)	0.122
Femoral access, n (%)	21 (16.8)	32 (25.6)	0.122
CIN, n (%)	12 (9.6)	25 (20.0)	0.033

Values are presented as mean \pm SD, median [IQR], or n (%), as appropriate. P-values were derived using an independent-samples t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables and chi-square test for categorical variables. CIN: contrast-induced nephropathy; NSTEMI: non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction; PCI: percutaneous coronary intervention; TyG: triglyceride-glucose.

Univariate analysis

When patients were stratified by the prespecified TyG threshold, those in the high-TyG group had a significantly greater frequency of CIN than those in the low-TyG group (25/125 [20.0%] vs 12/125 [9.6%]; chi-square $p = 0.033$). The unadjusted odds of CIN were more than twofold higher in the high-TyG group (OR 2.35, 95% CI 1.12-4.93), with a corresponding risk ratio of 2.08 (95% CI 1.10-3.96) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Incidence of contrast-induced nephropathy according to TyG group

Multivariable analysis

In the prespecified adjusted logistic regression model including TyG allocation, age, sex, baseline creatinine, and contrast volume, high TyG remained independently associated with CIN (adjusted OR 4.04, 95% CI 1.64-9.92; $p = 0.002$). Older age (per 10 years: adjusted OR 3.58, 95% CI 1.94-6.63; $p < 0.001$), higher baseline creatinine (per 0.1 mg/dL: adjusted OR 1.65, 95% CI 1.03-2.66; $p = 0.038$), and greater contrast volume (per 10 mL: adjusted OR 1.65, 95% CI 1.24-2.21; $p < 0.001$) were also independently associated with CIN, whereas sex was not (Table 2).

Table 2: Multivariable logistic regression analyses for predictors of contrast-induced nephropathy

Predictor	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
High TyG (>8.65)	4.04	1.64-9.92	0.002
Age (per 10 years)	3.58	1.94-6.63	<0.001
Male sex	0.65	0.27-1.58	0.342
Baseline creatinine (per 0.1 mg/dL)	1.65	1.03-2.66	0.038
Contrast volume (per 10 mL)	1.65	1.24-2.21	<0.001

In the sensitivity model replacing categorical allocation with the continuous TyG index, the TyG index also remained an independent predictor of CIN (adjusted OR 7.58 per 1-unit increase, 95% CI 2.32-24.73; $p < 0.001$). A kidney-function sensitivity model substituting eGFR for baseline creatinine yielded similar findings: high TyG remained significant (adjusted OR 4.11, 95% CI 1.67-10.15; $p = 0.002$), while lower eGFR independently predicted CIN (per 10 mL/min/1.73 m² increase: adjusted OR 0.54, 95% CI 0.31-0.95; $p = 0.032$).

Discussion

In the present study, a higher TyG index was associated with a significantly greater likelihood of contrast-induced nephropathy in non-diabetic patients with NSTEMI undergoing PCI, and this relationship remained significant after adjustment for age, sex, baseline renal function, and contrast volume. In practical terms, the study answers the research question in the affirmative: TyG is not merely correlated with CIN in this setting, but appears to function as an independent risk marker within a clinically important

subgroup in whom pre-procedural risk stratification is particularly valuable. This is meaningful because the current literature identified a consistent signal for TyG in broader PCI populations, but relatively limited validation in the exact population of non-diabetic NSTEMI patients undergoing PCI.⁹⁻¹¹

The magnitude of association observed in our cohort is clinically relevant. The unadjusted odds ratio of 2.35 and adjusted odds ratio of 4.04 suggest that TyG conveys substantial risk information even after accounting for conventional predictors. At the same time, our overall CIN incidence of 14.8% sits close to the 16% reported by Gursoy and Baydar and the 15.1% reported by Li et al., while remaining notably higher than the 6.6% observed by Aktas et al.^{7,9,10}. This pattern suggests that the signal is reproducible, but that absolute event rates and effect sizes are likely influenced by case-mix, local practice, and outcome definition. That issue is especially important here because our study protocol used a creatinine rise of > 0.3 mg/dL or > 50%, whereas Gursoy and Baydar, Aktas et al., and Li et al. used the more traditional 25% or 0.5 mg/dL framework, which may alter both incidence estimates and model performance^{7,9,10}.

Several aspects of the findings deserve closer interpretation. First, the high-TyG group in our cohort was modestly younger than the low-TyG group, yet still had a significantly higher CIN frequency. This is noteworthy because age is a well-established determinant of renal vulnerability, and the persistence of higher CIN rates in a younger but metabolically less favorable group suggests that TyG is capturing risk not explained by age alone. Second, fasting glucose and HbA1c did not differ significantly between CIN and non-CIN groups, whereas TyG did. In a non-diabetic population, this is biologically plausible: isolated glycemic measures may remain within relatively narrow ranges, while TyG better reflects the combined metabolic burden of subtle insulin resistance and atherogenic dyslipidemia. This interpretation is supported by Li et al., who showed that TyG outperformed HbA1c, fasting blood glucose, and triglycerides alone for CIN prediction and improved discrimination when added to a baseline model.⁷ Mechanistically, this also fits with contemporary views of CIN as a multifactorial process involving renal ischemia, direct tubular toxicity, and oxidative-inflammatory injury rather than hyperglycemia alone.^{4,5,8}

An additional point of interpretation is the contrast between association and discrimination. Although TyG remained independently associated with CIN in both the categorical and continuous models, the ROC performance in our study was modest, with an AUC of 0.633. This means that TyG is useful, but not sufficient as a standalone screening instrument. That nuance is important and should be emphasized rather than downplayed. Our empiric threshold

of approximately 8.90 was higher than the prespecified cutoff of 8.65 and closer to the thresholds reported by Li et al. (9.043) and Aktas et al. (9.17) than to the 8.69 operating point reported by GURSOY and Baydar.^{7,9,10} Taken together, these findings suggest that the biological relationship between TyG and CIN is robust, but that the most efficient decision threshold is probably population-dependent and influenced by local case-mix, renal criteria, and procedural practice.

Our findings are strongly supported by the most directly relevant studies cited in the thesis literature review. GURSOY and Baydar, in 350 non-diabetic NSTEMI patients undergoing PCI, reported TyG remaining independently associated with CIN (OR 2.5, 95% CI 1.3-4.6).⁹ Aktas et al., using a prospective design in 272 non-diabetic NSTEMI patients, showed a stepwise increase in CIN across TyG quartiles, from 1.5% in the lowest quartile to 13.2% in the highest, and reported a stronger independent association (OR 6.58, 95% CI 2.12-20.40) with an AUC of 0.712 at a cutoff of 9.17 [10]. In the broader NSTEMI-ACS PCI setting, Li et al. found that TyG was independently associated with CIN (adjusted OR 2.256, 95% CI 1.676-3.035), showed a J-shaped relationship with risk, and improved model AUC from 0.713 to 0.742 when added to a baseline model.⁷

Conclusion

this study demonstrates that a higher TyG index is significantly associated with an increased risk of contrast-induced nephropathy in non-diabetic patients presenting with NSTEMI and undergoing PCI. Patients with a TyG index >8.65 had a markedly higher frequency of CIN than those with lower values, and this association remained significant after adjustment for age, sex, baseline renal function, and contrast volume. These findings suggest that the TyG index captures clinically relevant metabolic vulnerability that is not fully explained by traditional renal and procedural risk factors alone.

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Author's contribution:

MA, MAA: Conceptualization of Project

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MAF: Writing of Manuscript